

Informed Consent Form

Title of the Research:

Developing the BcDEX Framework: A Design Science Research Approach to Blockchain Developer Experience

Principal Investigator: *Researcher Name, University Name [omitted for review]*

Contact Email: *Researcher Email [omitted for review]*

Phone: *Researcher Phone [omitted for review]*

1. Invitation to Participate

You are invited to voluntarily participate in an academic study about the experience of blockchain developers. This form provides essential information about the research and your rights as a participant.

2. Purpose of the Research

The objective of this study is to validate the BcDEX Framework, an instrument developed to measure, compare, and diagnose developer experience (DEX) in Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) platforms. Your feedback will help refine the framework regarding applicability and completeness.

3. Study Procedures

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to:

1. Complete a short questionnaire (5–10 minutes) about your professional background;
2. Participate in a 60–90 minute semi-structured interview via videoconference;
3. Evaluate framework constructs related to blockchain development experience;
4. Provide qualitative feedback on framework applicability in real-world scenarios.

4. Recording and Transcription

Interviews will be audio-recorded with your permission and later transcribed for qualitative analysis. You may request to stop recording or withdraw at any time. All files will be securely stored and deleted after study completion.

5. Risks and Discomforts

Risks are minimal and include possible discomfort discussing professional experiences or dedicating up to 90 minutes for the interview. You may withdraw at any time without penalty.

6. Benefits

Your participation contributes to advancing knowledge in blockchain developer experience. Benefits include early access to the research results and the opportunity for reflection on development practices. No financial compensation is provided.

7. Confidentiality and Anonymity

All personal data will remain confidential and anonymized in reports. Identifiers (e.g., names, companies) will be replaced with codes. Only the research team will access raw data. Direct quotations in publications will be anonymized.

8. Data Usage

Collected data will be used exclusively for academic purposes: qualitative analysis, research publications, doctoral thesis, and scientific presentations.

9. Voluntariness and Right to Withdraw

Participation is voluntary. You may refuse or withdraw consent at any time without consequence.

10. Results of the Research

A summary of results will be shared with all participants upon conclusion. Full results may be requested by email.

11. Consent Declaration

I, _____, declare that:

- I have read and understood this form;
- I had the opportunity to ask questions, and all were answered;
- I understand that my participation is voluntary;
- I agree to participate in this research.

Authorization for audio recording:

YES, I authorize the audio recording.

NO, I do not authorize recording.

Authorization for use of anonymous quotations:

YES, I authorize anonymous quotations.

NO, I do not authorize quotations.

Participant's Signature: _____ Date: ___/___/_____

Researcher's Signature: _____ Date: ___/___/_____